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External fine particle removal for crystallization processes: Introduction and systematic comparison with the temperature cycling-based fines removal

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ABSTRACT

Intermittent small particle removal is frequently used for particle property improvement in batch crystallization processes. This is generally solved by partial dissolution cycles, which for a cooling crystallization translates to temperature cycles - well suited for small-scale experimentation. However, implementing temperature cycles on a larger scale may face technical difficulties. This paper investigates a concept for fine particle removal, namely, the controlled external fines removal. Here, controlled dissolution is achieved in an external environment being attached to the crystallizer via a recirculation stream. Simulation-based external and internal fines removal is compared. The population balance model involves primary and secondary nucleation as well as crystal growth and dissolution. A two-level control system is developed: the low-level PI controller sets the vessel's temperature, whereas direct nucleation control (DNC) alternates between growth and dissolution cycles based on the actual particle number density. The paper demonstrates that the external fines' removal results in slightly but consistently larger particles and a narrower size distribution in the majority of cases. Under optimal conditions, external fines' removal leads to shorter batch times, and its convergence is significantly less sensitive to the DNC settings e.g., heating/cooling rates. From an energy utilization perspective, the internal fines removal requires less cooling and heating energy than the external configuration. The external configuration has great energy saving potential through heat integration as during the constant temperature recirculation the simultaneous heating and cooling duties in the crystallizer and heat exchanger match each other.

1. Introduction

Crystallization is widely used in chemical, food, and pharmaceutical industries not only for separation and purification but also as a particle formation technique due to its simplicity, good attainable yield as well as effectiveness at low temperatures for thermally labile compounds [1]. The particle size and shape fundamentally impact the downstream operations, such as filtration and drying, but also affects the bulk properties of the powder, e.g., the flowability, bulk density, or segregation propensity [2]. Furthermore, for pharmaceuticals, the specific particle surface area strongly impacts the dissolution rate, hence, the bioavailability of the ingredient [3]. Therefore, designing, and robustly operating crystallization processes improves the operability of the downstream processes as well as results in a product with the desired quality attributes. For this reason, numerous batch and continuous systems were designed and analyzed thoroughly [4].

Sub-processes, such as nucleation, and crystal growth may

simultaneously happen during a crystallization process, which is sometimes accompanied by secondary mechanisms including agglomeration and breakage. The particle properties are impacted by all these competing mechanisms. Therefore, a well-controlled crystallization drives the process through a trajectory that results in a delicate balance between various sub-processes, which ultimately results in the desired size distribution [5]. Practically, crystallization is often driven within the metastable zone, which is a relatively low supersaturation region dominated by crystal growth [6]. This permits the product size distribution adjustment with the seed properties. The necessary condition of keeping sufficiently low supersaturation is realized either with sufficiently slow cooling or by controlling the supersaturation directly [7]. Deployment of feedback control strategies became possible with the spread of process analytical technologies, including at larger than lab scales [8]. However, the rate of crystallization mechanisms as well as the metastable zone width is sensitive to the process conditions, such as stirring or the presence of impurities, which may hamper the

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performance of supersaturation control.

Repeated growth and dissolution cycles improve the particle properties, reduce the agglomeration degree as well as reduce the harmful effects of nucleation uncertainties [9–11]. Controlling the balance between the crystallization subprocesses with temperature cycles, e.g., finding the suitable temperature turning points and cooling/heating rates is challenging because both insufficient and excessive partial dissolution diverts the process from the desired path. Despite being a well-established methodology, new temperature cycling-based solutions are still being developed. Small-scale tubular reactors were recently applied for crystal shape modification [12] and complete deracemization of enantiomers [13]. A selective dissolution process featuring hydrocyclones was developed recently for crystal size control [14]. Temperature cycling implementing rapid microwave heating was developed for size-controlled crystallization [15] and temperature cycling aided deracemization [16] as well. Direct nucleation control (DNC) was proposed to control the relative particle number density (RND) in a feedback manner by repeated intermittent dissolution stages [17,18]. A great feature of DNC is that the cycle number and the turning points are self-adjusted. On the downside, the batch time is manipulated indirectly through the heating/cooling rates. Temperature cycles at scale may become challenging because of the thermal inertia of the slurry and the decreasing heat transfer area to slurry volume ratio. To overcome this obstacle, external fines removal is proposed here. Being a new realization of a powerful concept, a simulation study is carried out to investigate the feasibility of the concept.

Since its introduction [19], population balance modeling (PBM) has been successfully applied in crystallization engineering, from kinetics determination through process design and process control to the improvement of large-scale processes [20–24]. All the important crystallization mechanisms can be incorporated [25,26], and multiple internal particle properties can be considered [27,28]. Moreover, the numerical solution time is often fast enough for real-time applications [29], thus, the importance of PBMs in modern crystallization engineering can hardly be overestimated. Numerical studies represent great support when designing or operating crystallization processes [30,31]. When it comes to the evaluation or design of novel platforms, sometimes model-based investigations precede the experimental evaluation, as happened for example in the case of wet-mill integrated crystallization processes recently [32,33].

This study aims to introduce and numerically analyze the concept of controlled fines removal using an external dissolution environment. DNC is applied as a high-level controller, removing the fines selectively by recirculating the slurry through an external heat exchanger. The process is analyzed from the basics such as low-level temperature controller tuning to the analysis of the operation and product property-related aspects. Finally, an illustrative energetic analysis is carried out. The widely used and accepted internal fines removal is used as a comparison basis at all stages of this work.

2. Direct nucleation control: internal and external solutions

The controlled variable of the system is the specific number density (SND), which is inversely proportional to the particle size, whereas the controlled variable is the temperature. The setpoint is specified as a target SND with a corresponding lower and upper bound. DNC relies on fuzzy-like control rules: when the actual SND is below the lower bound, the system is in a growth regime. With reasonable cooling rates, this will result in increasing supersaturation, which may exceed the metastable limit, triggering secondary nucleation. This will raise the actual RND beyond the upper bound. At that point, the DNC automatically initiates a dissolution cycle, which is continued until the RND decreases to the lower bound. The DNC aims to keep the actual value between the pre-set bounds. The nucleation can be forced back if the supersaturation is kept within the metastable zone, which is promoted by reducing the cooling rate whenever the actual RND is between the bounds.

Fig. 1. Proposed setups and control loops for internal and external fines removal for cooling crystallization processes.

Traditionally, the DNC in cooling crystallization is realized in a jacketed cooling crystallizer, attached to a heating/cooling thermostat. The setpoint for the temperature controller is provided by the DNC (see Fig. 1a). Implementing temperature cycles at scale may become problematic as the heat transfer area to the slurry volume of jacketed crystallizers decreases with the reactor dimensions. Physical separation of growth and dissolution offers a workaround: as Fig. 1b illustrates, an external heat exchanger may be applied for dissolution, which is integrated into the crystallizer with a recirculation loop. The pump may be placed downstream of the heat exchanger where the stream is undersaturated, to prevent clogging issues. A simple operation is proposed: growth regime is realized with crystallizer cooling, without recirculation. In dissolution mode, the crystallizer temperature is constant, whereas a constant recirculation exists through the higher temperature heat exchanger.

Since the residence time distribution of a continuous tank crystallizer is not monodisperse, it takes more batch turnovers until all the solution passes at least once the external heat exchanger. To illustrate this, let us assume that the homogeneous hypothesis describes the hydrodynamics of the tank (which was verified to be a good approximation in this case). Furthermore, if the external heat exchanger does not introduce transport delay, the fraction of solution that did not pass the heat exchanger (ω) can be calculated analytically as a function of the number of batch turnovers (N_{tb}):

$$\omega = 1 - \exp(-N_{tb}) \quad (1)$$

Given the Eq. (1), assuming fast dissolution, some particles will

Fig. 2. Scheme of a) tubular heat exchanger as external dissolver; b) TIS approximation of the tubular heat exchanger with units N . Q denotes a characteristic tank dimension (e.g., slurry volume, jacket volume, and heat transfer area).

undergo more dissolution cycles than others, and the longer the dissolution loop is being operated, the stronger this effect becomes. This last statement has direct implications on the CSD due to the size-dependent dissolution (larger particles have a higher dissolution rate, see Eq. (8)). In a mixed product removal system, the probability that a small and a large particle is withdrawn and pushed through the heat exchanger is identical. However, given the size-dependent dissolution behavior, the larger particles shrink more having two consequences: (i) more batch turnovers are required to fully dissolve the fine particles, (ii) the relative standard deviation of the CSD decreases when passes through the heat exchanger. This represents a major difference between the internal and external fines' removal operation. It is worthwhile to underline the importance of unclassified removal: removing the crystals from the bottom of the crystallizer may inherently result in preferential removal of larger crystals, which hampers the fine elimination performance of the loop. This can be avoided for example by optimizing the position of the discharge system within the reactor [34].

3. Process model and numerical solution

It is assumed that primary and secondary nucleation, crystal growth, and dissolution take place. Cooling crystallization is considered, and the temperature dependency of solubility (c_s) being described with the exponential equation [35]:

$$c_s = a_1 \exp(a_2 T_K) \quad (2)$$

where T_K is the temperature in kelvin. The supersaturation ratio (S) is the main driving force of the crystallization, which is expressed as the ratio of actual concentration (c) and solubility:

$$S = \frac{c}{c_s} \quad (3)$$

The primary nucleation rate (B_p) is described by the temperature-dependent Volmer-Weber equation [36]:

$$B_p = k_p \exp\left(-\frac{k_c}{\ln^2 S}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{E_p}{RT_K}\right) \quad (4)$$

The secondary nucleation rate (B_s) is assumed to be a linear function of the crystals volume fraction and a power-law equation is used to describe its rate:

$$B_s = k_s (c - c_s)^g V_c \quad (5)$$

The specific surface area of crystals (V_c) is defined as:

$$V_c = k_v \int_0^\infty L^3 n(L) dL \quad (6)$$

k_v being the volume shape factor. The growth rate (G) is assumed to be supersaturation and size-dependent [37]:

$$G = k_g (c - c_s)^g (1 + p_g L)^{\gamma_g} \quad (7)$$

The dissolution rate (D) is given by a similar equation [38]:

$$D = k_d (c_s - c)^d (1 + p_d L)^{\gamma_d} \quad (8)$$

The overall mass transfer rate between the solid and liquid (R_V) can be described as:

$$R_V = \begin{cases} k_v \rho_c \left[3 \int_0^\infty GL^2 n(L) dL + (B_p + B_s) L_n^3 \right], & \text{if } \sigma > 0 \\ -3k_v \rho_c \int_0^\infty DL^2 n(L) dL, & \text{if } \sigma < 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The dynamics of the crystal size distribution (CSD), solute concentration, and temperature under the influence of nucleation, growth, and dissolution are described by the population, mass, and energy balance equations, presented in the supporting information of this paper. The tubular heat exchanger is modeled using the tank-in-series (TIS) approximation, as Fig. 2 illustrates. This was necessary for implementation reasons in Simulink.

The solubility equation and parameters are from the work by [35]. The kinetic parameters for secondary nucleation, crystal growth, and dissolution are taken from the literature [38,37]. Since these studies did not account for, primary nucleation kinetics were taken from another paper [39]. This latter paper uses a different model compound. Hence, from a macroscopic perspective, the model represents a hypothetical system having realistic behavior. A lab-scale (0.5 L) crystallizer is considered with a 5.5 mm wide external tube in a tube heat exchanger. The derivation of exact dimensions for the crystallizer and heat exchanger can be found in the supporting information. Based on the

Fig. 3. Simulated behavior of internal and jacket temperatures, concentrations and third moments of the distribution in the heat exchanger: a) transients and b) steady states.

calculations it is obvious that the heat transfer area to volume of the heat exchanger is significantly higher than that of the crystallizer.

The model equations were solved with a high-resolution finite volume method (HR-FVM), which is a generic technique for the numerical solution of hyperbolic partial differential equations [40], and it was shown to be suitable for the solution of PB equations (PBEs) [41]. Utilizing the FVM was necessary to handle the dissolution of the crystals. For simplicity but without losing the generality, averaged particle properties are utilized in the data interpretation. The k^{th} moment of the distribution (μ_k) is defined as:

$$\mu_k = \int_0^{\infty} L^k n(L) dL, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (10)$$

The zeroth moment ($k = 0$) gives the SND of crystals ($\#/m^3$). The third moment ($k = 3$) is an important quantity, being proportional to the specific volume fraction of crystals (m^3/m^3), see Eq. (6). The mean particle size (\hat{L}) and standard deviation (σ), both expressed in m, are calculated in terms of moments as:

$$\hat{L} = \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_0}$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_2}{\mu_0} - \left(\frac{\mu_1}{\mu_0}\right)^2} \quad (11)$$

The dynamics of the batch cooling crystallization have been analyzed thoroughly *via* simulations [42,43], but only a handful of studies implied PBMs for simulation of distributed parameter systems [44]. To demonstrate the capability of the TIS-based heat exchanger simulation, let us consider the situation of heat exchanger start-up. The heat exchanger and jacket temperatures are 20 °C initially, the concentration is the solubility at 20 °C, and there are no crystals. At time zero, the heating is started (with heating agent temperature and flowrate of 90 °C and $2 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$), whereas the feeding stream is initiated (with temperature, concentration, and flow rate of 20 °C, saturation concentration at 20 °C, and $2.67 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, and crystals having a normal size distribution with a mean and standard deviation of 100 and 50 μm , and a volume fraction of 0.1). The simulation results are summarized in Fig. 3, where the left-hand side images illustrate the temporal and spatial evolution of temperatures, concentrations, and third moments, and the right-hand side figures depict the steady states along the length of the heat exchanger. The complete particle dissolution was achieved as revealed by the fact that the third moment decreased to (nearly) zero in the last segment of the heat exchanger (bottom right). Simultaneously with the decrease of the third moment, the solute concentration increases proportionally, where the proportionality constant is the shape factor (k_v).

Clearly, the TIS approach is suitable for the dynamic simulation of the dissolution in the counter-current tubular heat exchanger.

4. Control system design and tuning

In the case of internal fines removal, the manipulated variable of the top-level controller is the crystallizer temperature, which is modulated between constant heating and cooling states, realized with a PI controller. The controlled variable of the PI controller is the crystallizer temperature, which is realized by manipulating the heating or cooling agent's flow rate. The crystallizer is water-cooled, and two, constant temperature sources are available (hot and cold). For positive control inputs the hot, and for negative control inputs, the cold source is utilized (Fig. 1a). For external fines removal, the top-level controller achieves external fines removal by stopping the cooling and fixing the crystallizer temperature simultaneously with turning the constant recirculation on through the heat exchanger. The low-level PI temperature controllers manipulate the cold source entering the crystallizer jacket and the hot

Fig. 4. Optimization-based controller tuning: temperature control behavior in the crystallizer in a) internal and b) external fines removal.

source entering the heat exchanger jacket (Fig. 1b).

The PI controllers are tuned for setpoint tracking, based on optimization. In the optimization, a pre-defined temperature profile is utilized, and the goal is to find the PI parameters (P) that simultaneously minimize the deviations from the setpoint and the noisiness of the control signal. $P = [K_c, T_i]$ for the internal, and $P = [K_{c,c}, T_{i,c}, K_{c,h}, T_{i,h}]$ for external fines removal. The subscripts for the external fines' removal case denote the crystallizer (c) and heat exchanger (h). The goal function is:

$$O(P) = wO_1(P) + (1 - w)O_2(P) \quad (12)$$

The weight factor w was chosen systematically for the two cases, which is described in detail in the supporting information. The first term of Eq. (11) is related to the error integral whereas the second characterizes the noisiness of the control action:

Fig. 5. Typical internal and external fines removal processes. a) evolution of SND and the temperature; b) evolution of mean crystal sizes; c) evolution of standard deviations of particle sizes. SND bounds: $0.9 \cdot 10^{10}$ – $1.1 \cdot 10^{10}$; heating/cooling rate: $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$; recirculation rate: $16 \text{ mL}/\text{min}$.

$$O_1(\mathbf{P}) = \frac{1}{t_{\max}} \int_0^{t_{\max}} (PV(t) - PV_{sp}(t))^2 dt$$

$$O_2(\mathbf{P}) = \frac{1}{t_{\max}} \int_0^{t_{\max}} \left(\frac{F(t)}{dt} \right)^2 dt \quad (13)$$

where PV denotes the process variable (the controlled temperatures), whereas F stands for the manipulated variable (heating and cooling water flowrates). The obtained optimal tuning parameters are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 4 depicts the temperature dynamics of the crystallizer in the two configurations: the setpoint is followed tightly in both cases, making the controllers suitable for low-level temperature tracking. There is a moderate noise in the jacket flowrates, which is the maximal level that was allowed in the controller tuning (see the supporting information for more details).

The high-level SND controllers have two parameters: the heating/cooling rates and a controller gain, considering the attenuation of cooling/heating rates when the actual SND is between the bounds. The gain factor is set to 2 in all simulations. The systematic determination of the suitable heating/cooling rates is difficult, due to the non-linear nature of the crystallization process. From a practical perspective, one must consider the physical limits of heat transfer. The highest heating/cooling rates applied in this work are $1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Too low heating/cooling rates translate to excessive batch time, which is undesired from an economic perspective. Hence, the minimal rate used in this study is $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. For a fair comparison, for each target SND, ten DNC simulations are realized in the 0.1 – $1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ domain with $0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ increment. This allows to find the minimal batch time, and hence, to compare the two systems under optimal productivity conditions.

5. Particle size control via internal and external fines removal

The starting and terminal conditions, such as the seed load and size, initial temperature and supersaturation, final temperature, and DNC setpoint of the two configurations are identical. The heat exchanger's initial concentration matches the crystallizer's overall solute content (including the amount of dissolved solute and the seed). This ensures that the overall solute mass in the crystallizer is not impacted by the heat exchanger, thus, the results between the internal and external fines removal remain comparable.

A demonstrative simulation is presented in Fig. 5, depicting the implemented temperature profiles together with the evolution of SNDs, mean crystal sizes, and standard deviations. The target SND was realized in both strategies: the internal and external fines' removal implemented two, and, respectively, three dissolution cycles. The SND target was reached at relatively high temperatures without further nucleation during the cooling stage, meaning that the process was driven within the metastable zone at this stage. The effects of dissolution cycles on mean particle size and the standard deviation are illustrated in Figs. 5b and c. It is important to realize that the SND is identical in both processes starting from the sixth hour, yet the deviations in the size distributions are considerable. This is explained in the discussions related to Eq. (1).

Once the product quality is met, productivity becomes a key economic indicator. Under the circumstances utilized in these simulations, productivity is inversely proportional to the batch time. The batch time is impacted by the heating/cooling rates: on one hand, faster rates can translate to shorter batch time but on the other hand, with faster cooling the metastable limit is crossed with higher likelihood, triggering the time-consuming dissolution cycle. For each target SND, ten simulations were carried out with heating/cooling rates in the 0.1 – $1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ range. Such simulation is presented in Fig. 5. At each simulation, the time at which the final temperature is reached is recorded as batch time. The particle properties are recorded at 60 min following the batch time to

a)

b)

Fig. 6. a) Determination of the minimally achievable batch times for internal and external fines' removal. Target SND: $5 \cdot 10^{10}$; b) comparison of minimally attainable batch times and the resulting product properties in a wide range of SND targets. The lower and upper SND bounds are 90 and 110% of the target SND in all cases.

ensure that the solution is de-supersaturated. Finally, the cooling rate at which the minimal batch time is realized is considered the optimal DNC setting for maximal productivity (Fig. 6a). The minimally attainable batch times and the corresponding particle properties are determined for a broad target SND domain, which results in reasonable mean particle sizes for typical pharmaceutical products. According to Fig. 6b, the external fines' removal realized shorter operating times regardless of the SND target, and part from the lowest SND target also resulted in larger mean particle sizes. This, under controlled SND conditions, is possible if the CSD is narrower, which is also supported by Fig. 6b. From an application perspective, monomodal CSD with narrow distribution almost always represents higher product quality. Hence, external fine removal realized higher product quality in a process with greater productivity in 90% of the considered cases.

Table 1

Model parameters utilized in the process simulations: thermodynamic, kinetic constants, and the dimensions of the crystallizer and the heat exchanger.

Symbol	Meaning, unit	Value
a_1	Solubility model parameter, -	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$
a_2	Solubility model parameter, -	$3.07 \cdot 10^{-2}$
k_p	Primary nucleation rate constant, $\#/(m^3s)$	$1.15 \cdot 10^{21}$
k_e	Primary nucleation rate parameter, -	0.16
E_p	Primary nucleation rate activation energy, J/mol	$7.67 \cdot 10^4$
k_s	Secondary nucleation rate constant, $\#/(m^3s)$	$3.80 \cdot 10^{16}$
s	Secondary nucleation exponent, -	3.41
k_g	Growth rate constant, m/s	$8.57 \cdot 10^{-6}$
g	Growth rate exponent, -	1.00
p_g	Growth rate size dependent parameter, 1/m	$5.00 \cdot 10^3$
γ_g	Growth rate size exponent, -	1.57
k_d	Dissolution rate constant, m/s	$1.28 \cdot 10^6$
d	Dissolution rate exponent, -	0.98
p_d	Dissolution rate size dependent parameter, 1/m	$2.00 \cdot 10^4$
γ_d	Dissolution rate size exponent, -	0.86
k_V	Volume shape factor, -	$\pi/6$
ρ_c	Crystal density, kg/m^3	$1.30 \cdot 10^3$
ρ_s	Solvent density, kg/m^3	$9.98 \cdot 10^2$
$c_{p,c}$	Crystal specific heat, J/(kg K)	$1.38 \cdot 10^3$
$c_{p,s}$	Solvent specific heat, J/(kg K)	$4.18 \cdot 10^3$
H_c	Heat of crystallization, J/kg	$1.85 \cdot 10^5$
V	Crystallizer volume, m^3	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
A	Crystallizer heat transfer area, m^2	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-2}$
V_j	Crystallizer jacket volume, m^3	$7.62 \cdot 10^{-5}$
V_h	Heat exchanger volume, m^3	$6.67 \cdot 10^{-5}$
V_{jh}	Heat exchanger jacket volume, m^3	$5.76 \cdot 10^{-5}$
D_h	Heat exchanger diameter, m	$5.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$
L_h	Heat exchanger length, m	2.77
A_h	Heat exchanger surface area, m^2	$2.73 \cdot 10^{-2}$
T_c	Nominal coolant temperature, °C	10
T_h	Nominal heating agent temperature, °C	90
U	Heat transfer coefficient, $W/(m^2K)$	800
U_L	Heat transfer coefficient between the vessels and the surroundings, $W/(m^2K)$	1

* the cooling and heating agents have the same properties as the solvent.

It is noteworthy that for internal fines' removal there is no data for 0.5 °C/min cooling rate and beyond in Fig. 6a. The reason is that in these cases the temperature did not converge to the target value (20 °C) in the considered maximal batch time (18 h). This means that the system entered a sustained oscillatory, or slowly dampened oscillatory regime. Such simulation is included in the supporting information of this paper as a demonstration, but in general, the phenomenon is not unknown, it generally appears at relatively high cooling rates [45]. According to Table 3, external fines' removal did not show such unstable behavior under the investigated conditions. In contrast, instabilities appeared at all target SNDs for internal fines' removal, which was more prone to oscillations at lower SND setpoints.

6. Energy demand comparison

Temperature cycling is associated with excess energy demand compared to the pure cooling strategies. A simple analysis is performed to estimate the energy demands. The calculations assume that the heat transfer fluid is being recirculated to a thermostat that brings the temperature back to its nominal desired level. A low and a high-temperature thermostat is available, which allows a quick switchover between heating and cooling regimes in the internal fines' removal (see Fig. 1a). The heating and cooling circuits are separated physically in the external configuration. In the internal fines' removal operation, the evacuated coolant is connected to the cooling thermostat in cooling mode and *vice-versa* to maintain constant heat transfer fluid volumes. Nevertheless, this leaves further room for energetic optimization, and it was considered due to its practical simplicity.

The Q_s specific energy demand (J/m^3 suspension) for t operating time

Table 2
Optimal parameters of the parallel PI controllers.

System	Control loop	Controller gain (-)	Integral gain (-)
Batch	Crystallizer	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$2.61 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Integrated	Crystallizer	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$5.17 \cdot 10^{-9}$
	Heat exchanger	$0.90 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-9}$

and V operating volume is calculated as a function of T_r reference temperature (that is the nominal temperature of the heat transfer agent, see Table 1), T_j actual jacket temperature and $F(t)$ actual flow rate (m^3/s).

$$Q_s = \frac{\rho c_p}{V} \int_0^t F(t)(T_j(t) - T_r) dt \quad (14)$$

For ρ density and c_p specific heat capacity, the water's properties are utilized, that is, 1000 kg/m^3 and, respectively, 4186 J/(kg K) . Hence, the simulation of $F(t)$ and $T(t)$ permits the calculation of hot and cold stream heat flows throughout the processes, as presented in Fig. 7. Recirculation generates roughly an order of magnitude surge in cooling and heating duty compared to the standard temperature control. This is explained as the recirculated stream transfers the cold slurry from the crystallizer to the heat exchanger, where its intensively heated, followed by the recirculation to the crystallizer, where it should be cooled back to the crystallizer's temperature. The greater the temperature difference between the crystallizer and the heat exchanger and the greater the flow rate is, the more simultaneous heating and cooling energy is required for the operation.

Table 4 compares the overall energy demand of the processes depicted in Fig. 7. The internal configuration requires less than a fifth of the external configuration's demand. The table breaks down the demands of external configuration to show the excess duty of the dissolution cycle. This could be reduced with an energy-focused operation: a lower temperature gap between the crystallizer and heat exchanger may be sufficient to achieve dissolution, which would simultaneously reduce the cooling and heating duty. Furthermore, simultaneous cooling and heating happen, opening doors for heat integration by the application of heat pumps, which can further reduce the large energy demand of the recirculation loop. Nevertheless, this requires further investment costs. Whether it is worth the investment or not can be estimated by detailed techno-economic calculations, which are outside the scopes of this paper [46].

Since the energy demand of the external configuration exceeded considerably the internal configuration's demand, no broader analyses were carried out as the conclusions are not expected to change fundamentally. That is, the batch configuration has lower energy demand, but the external configuration inherently fulfills all criteria for heat integration, which could be optimized to reduce the energy demand significantly.

Table 3

Comparison of internal and external fines' removal processes from the point of view of control loop stability. The process is said to be converged if the final temperature is reached within 18 h (convergence in external/internal fines' removal; 1 = yes, 0 = no).

SND target ($\#/\text{m}^3$)	Cooling/heating rate ($^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$)									
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
$1 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$2 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$3 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$4 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$5 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$6 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$7 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0	1/0
$8 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0
$9 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0	1/0
$10 \cdot 10^{10}$	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/0	1/0

Of course, one could argue that heat integration could be applied in batch temperature cycling as well. However, integration normally implies using another stream of the process that similarly needs heating or cooling but in the case of batches the system is not at steady-state and it would be difficult to find a collection of streams that would consistently provide exactly the demands of the crystallization process, which in this case are time-variant due to the thermal cycles.

7. Conclusions

In this study, the concept of DNC via external fines removal was introduced as well as the subject of model-based analysis and comparison with the internal DNC. For obtaining realistic simulation results, the crystallization kinetics validated with experimental data was taken from the literature. The PBE-based model of the cooling crystallization process involves primary and secondary nucleation, as well as size-dependent growth and dissolution mechanisms. Beyond the PBE and the associated energy and mass balances, the energy balance of the jacket is also considered, enabling the simulation of the PI control loop. The partial dissolution cycles are realized by implementing temperature cycles in the internal, and external heat exchanger connected with a recirculation loop in the external fines' removal configuration. The systematic comparison revealed that the external fines' removal is more robust concerning DNC settings: meanwhile the higher heating and cooling rates translated to oscillatory control in roughly half of the analyzed cases of internal configuration, and no such instabilities were observed at the external DNC. Furthermore, the external fines' removal generally resulted in shorter batch times and products characterized by larger mean size (up to $15\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$, that was in the range of 10%) and narrower size distribution. An energetic analysis revealed that the heating and cooling demand of the external configuration significantly exceeded the energy consumption of the internal DNC, but for the external DNC there is clear potential for the application of heat pumps between the crystallizer and the external heat exchanger to considerably reduce the overall energy demand. Whether the improved product particle properties, shorter batch time, and more stable operation are worth the investment of the external heat exchanger, the heat integration, and the higher energy demand or not may be a subject of techno-economic analysis, with outcomes depending on product price and production scale, as well as energy costs and availability.

Author contribution statement

The sole author, Botond Szilágyi did all the work related to this paper.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

a)

b)

Fig. 7. Heating and cooling demands of the crystallization processes of Fig. 5. a) internal fines' removal; b) external fines' removal.

Table 4

Comparison of the internal and external fines removal experiments of Fig. 5. from an energetic standpoint.

Energy demand	Energy demand (kWh/m ³ of slurry)		Dissolution regime
	Internal	External	
	Growth regime		
Heating	52.2	14.5	247.8
Cooling	34.8	31.5	201.0

the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.cep.2022.109074.

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